

Amylose content was highest in IET4094 and lowest in IET2254. The elongation ratio of milled rice ranged between 1.74 (IR36) and 1.22 (CR237-1).

Highest volume expansion during cooking was in the CN747-8-1 and highest water uptake was in IET1444. IR42 expanded least and had low water uptake. □

Grain characteristics of some aromatic rice varieties of Assam

K. K. Sarma, T. Ahmed, and D. K Baruah, Regional Agricultural Research Station, Titabar, Assam, India

Scented rice is grown by farmers in Assam for the preparation of special holiday foods. We studied awning, pigmentation, length/breadth (L/B) ratio, and 1,000-grain weight of 43 traditional scented varieties in 1988. Thirteen possessed awns and 23 were pigmented. Grain length was 5.66-9.94 mm, breadth 1.80-2.96 mm, L/B ratio 2.44-4.33, and 1,000-grain weight 8.44-25.48 g. □

Pest resistance – diseases

Blast (BI) resistance in tidal swamp rices of Indonesia

M. Hamda, Banjarbaru Research Institute for Food Crops, P.O. Box 31, Banjarbaru, South Kalimantan, Indonesia

We evaluated field resistance to B1 caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* in 158 rices during the 1988 wet season.

Each line was transplanted at 20- × 20-cm spacing. Plots were fertilized with urea and triple superphosphate at 120-26 kg NP/ha. Disease scoring was one 30 d after transplanting.

None of the varieties tested were resistant; 33 were moderately resistant (MR) (see table). □

Pest resistance–insects

Reaction of rice varieties to gall midge (GM)

M. P. Singh, Entomology Department, Manipur Agricultural College, Iroiseмба, Imphal 795001, Manipur, India

We field-tested 137 rice varieties and breeding lines for resistance to GM during 1987-88 wet seasons. Seedlings were transplanted 1 mo after seeding in two 4-m rows/variety at 20- × 20-cm spacing. Susceptible check TN1 was planted every 20 rows. Local recommended agronomic practices were followed.

GM incidence and damage were recorded 30 and 50 d after transplanting. Susceptible check TN1 had an average 75% infested hills and 29% silvershoots at 50 d after transplanting.

Eleven entries were found to be highly resistant to GM, three showed moderate resistance (see table).

Rice GM resistance in Manipur, India, 1987-88 wet seasons.

Cultivar	Cross	Resistance rating ^a
R320-300	Asha/Kranti	0
R321-108	Samridhi/IR36	0
RP2436-79-22-2	IR50/WGL 22508	0
WGL 18011-15	CR44/WGL 12708	0
WGL 20471-97	BC5/WGL 12708	0
WGL 26358	IR20/WGL 12708	0
BPT3624	BPT3361/WGL 26888	0
W1263	MTU15/Eswarakora	0
Aganni	Donor	0
T1477	Donor	0
Banglei	Donor	0
WGL 3011-120	WGL 22509/IR50	3
WGL 47998	Obs 677/IR2070	3
R320-101	Asha/Kranti	3
TN1	Susceptible check	9

^aScale 0-9 based on *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

Reaction of tidal swamp rices to Bl. Unit Tatas, Central Kalimantan, Indonesia, 1988 wet season.

Line	Disease score	Reaction
BRB4-29-3	3	MR
BR51-120-2	3	MR
BW100	3	MR
BW295-4	3	MR
BW295-5	3	MR
B3240 ENG 4	3	MR
Cisadane	3	MR
CR1002	3	MR
IR13149-3-2-2	3	MR
IR13149-43-2	3	MR
IR13423-17-1-2-1	3	MR
IR21820-154-3-2-2-3	3	MR
IR2307-247-2-2-3	3	MR
IR28222-9-2-2-2-2	3	MR
IR28223-399-5-6	3	MR
IR31662-47-2-1	3	MR
IR4-11	3	MR
IR4417-179-1-5-2	3	MR
IR4422-480-2-2-3	3	MR
IR4432-52-6-4	3	MR
IR5785-188-2-1	3	MR
IR9217-6-2-2-2-3	3	MR
P1277-7-14M-5-1B	3	MR
P1342-6-10M-3-1B	3	MR
ROHY B15-WAR-3-3	3	MR
ROK5	3	MR
IR28288-12-3-1-1-2	3	MR
B4460H-MR-6	3	MR
IR19661	3	MR
Kapuas	3	MR
Cisanggarung	3	MR
BRB50-13-2-1	3	MR
DWCB-B-27-2	3	MR

Effect of temperature and storage on yellow stem borer (YSB) egg hatchability and larval survival

V. D. Viajante and R. C. Saxena, Entomology Department, IIRI

Routine YSB cultures on caged plants sometimes cannot supply enough newly emerged larvae for yield-loss studies. Egg masses produced by females collected in light traps are needed. To synchronize larval emergence with experimental needs, embryonic development must be suspended. We experimented to determine the temperature regime during incubation that would not affect egg hatchability and larval survival.

Newly emerged YSB moths reared in the field on caged IR46 rice plants were collected daily and caged for oviposition on 30-d-old IR36 plants. Egg masses of uniform size were collected daily and placed singly in test tubes with a moist cotton pad at the bottom. One egg mass represented one replication. The test tubes with egg